

CARING AND CAREGIVERS

Dr. Md. Amanuallah
Assistant Professor
Dept. of Clinical Neurosciences
College of Medicine
King Faisal University
Kingdom of Saudi Arabia

Paper Type: Article

"Doctor diagnose nurses heal, and caregiver make Sense of it all."

(Brett H. Lewis)

Caregivers and Consequences are closely related in the context of overloaded burden and responsibilities. The influence of caring has been seen on health and well-being of caregivers by studies. It has well documented that stress and perceived situation of personal danger or threatening have produced anxious behavior. Similarly, caregivers or spouses reported stress, anxiety and depression during their care given duties. Evidence suggests that "caregivers with HIV or other illness may be particularly vulnerable to stress and poor mental health" (Breuer, Myer, Struthers, & Joska, 2011; Prince et al., 2007; Silver, Bauman, Camacho, & Hudis, 2003; Surkan et al., 2010). Grunfeld et al., quoted that "family members provide a considerable amount of the care for people with terminal illnesses and their own health may suffer as a consequence".

In those "long-term care conditions, caregiving has a dramatic impact on the health and well-being of family caregivers. Between 40% and 70% of caregivers have been found to have clinically significant levels of depressive symptoms, and as many as 50% may meet criteria for a diagnosable depressive disorder at some point in their care giving careers" (Friss LR, Whitlatch CJ, 1991; Gallagher D, Rose J, Rivera P, Lovett S, Thompson LW, 1989; Pruchno RA, Resch NL, 1989; Redinbaugh EM, MacCallum RC, Kiecolt-Glaser JK, 1995; Schulz R, O'Brien AT, Bookwala J, Fleissner K.,1995; Whitlatch CJ, Feinberg LF, Sebesta DS, 1997). The task of caring becomes increasingly difficult as per the severity of the diseases. Hence, some risk factors influence the caregiver's quality of life and increase the burden. Identified risk

factors, connected with the caregivers such as unbalanced emotional well-being, lack of stamina, poor health condition, lack of support. On the other hand, caring profession also have risk factors reported by (Bane, (n.d) "several risk factors which may lead the stress of caring like gender plays a role because more woman is entering and staying in the workforce longer, delaying childbearing, experiencing escalating divorce rates, and becoming single parents -- leaving them with responsibilities for several generations of caregiving. Additionally, relationships can be complicated and conflict within families often initiates stress. Loss of loved ones, relocation, job/career changes (retirement, no advancement, increased workload), and financial burdens may be stressors for caring. Likewise, current events or catastrophic illnesses or accidents will undoubtedly lead to difficulties. Lack of adequate rest, exercise, diet, recreation, and socialization may cause undue stress" (Bane, (n.d).

Thus, platforms like sharing, positive assistance, inspirations are important to caregivers as well as adequate coping strategies also relatively significant in this context. The physician should have to encourage the coping styles of caregivers or spouses and to appreciate the importance of his/her own needs. "Positive communication, expand of quality time, yoga, music, sharing with a friend, coping with negative emotions e.g. anger, envy, annoyance" also recommended. As williams & kay (1995) quoted that identification of own limits can apply by caregivers to foster the quality of life and capabilities of caregivers.

References:

- Bane, S. D. (n.d). Mental Health and Aging, p. 103-107.
<http://cas.umkc.edu/casww/rewdstrs.htm>
- Breuer E, Myer L, Struthers H, Joska J. HIV/AIDS and mental health research in sub-Saharan Africa: a systematic review. *African Journal of AIDS Research*. 2011; 10(2):101–122.
- Prince M, Patel V, Saxena S, Maj M, Maselko J, Phillips M, Rahman A. No health without mental health. *The Lancet*. 2007; 370(9590):859–877.

Silver E, Bauman L, Camacho S, Hudis J. Factors Associated with Psychological Distress in Urban Mothers with Late-Stage HIV/AIDS. *AIDS and Behavior*. 2003; 7(4):421–431. [PubMed: 14707539]

Surkan P, Mukherjee J, Williams D, Eustache E, Louis E, Jean-Paul T, Fawzi M. Perceived Discrimination and stigma toward children affected by HIV/AIDS and their HIV-positive Caregivers in central Haiti. *AIDS Care*. 2010; 22(7):803–815. [PubMed: 20635244]

Grunfeld E, Coyle D, Whelan T, Clinch J, Reyno L, Earle CC, et al. Family caregiver burden: results of a longitudinal study of breast cancer patients and their principal caregivers. *CMAJ* 2004; 170(12):1795-801.

Friss LR, Whitlatch CJ. Who's taking care? A statewide study of family caregivers. *Am J Alzheimers Care Related Dis Res* 1991; 6:16-26.

Gallagher D, Rose J, Rivera P, Lovett S, Thompson LW. Prevalence of depression in family caregivers. *Gerontologist* 1989; 29:449-56

Pruchno RA, Resch NL. Aberrant behaviors and Alzheimer's disease: mental health effects on spouse caregivers. *J Gerontol* 1989; 44(5): S177-S82.

Redinbaugh EM, MacCallum RC, Kiecolt-Glaser JK. Recurrent syndromal depression in caregivers. *Psychol Aging* 1995; 10:358-68.

Schulz R, O'Brien AT, Bookwala J, Fleissner K. Psychiatric and physical morbidity effects of dementia caregiving: prevalence, correlates, and causes

Whitlatch CJ, Feinberg LF, Sebesta DS. Depression and health in family caregivers: adaptation over time. *J Aging Health* 1997; 9(2):222-43.

Mental Health and Aging, Bane, S. D., p. 103-107. : <http://cas.umkc.edu/casww/rewdsters.htm>
Williams, G. B. & Kay, P. (1995). *The Caregiver's Manual: A Guide to Helping the Elderly and Infirm*. Carol Publishing Group: New York, NY.